

Analysis of Strain-Energy-Release Rates for Unidirectional Graphite/Epoxy Laminates with Separated Central Plies Under Fatigue Loading.

Rudolf Prinz

(Deutsche Forschungs- und Versuchsanstalt für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Institut für Strukturmechanik, 3300 Braunschweig - Flughafen, Germany)

Ligun Cao

(Chinese Aircraft Establishment, Aeromaterial Research Institute, Beijing, China)

Abstract

For the determination of *strain energy release rates* and *stress intensity factors* of graphite/epoxy continuous fiber laminates of unidirectional stacking order were used whose central plies were separated prior to curing. Such laminates are referred to as $[0_m/\phi_n]_s$, the slash indicating the cut. In the course of cycling loading a lateral crack developed in the area of the separations from which two delaminations initiated at each of the interfaces of the separated and the continuous plies. For the *stiffness/delamination-length relation* a simple equation was derived. The results obtained from this approach compared very favorably with a finite element calculation so that the energy release rate G_{II} for this type of delamination can be determined rather accurately from the simple equation. For the cyclic energy release rate ΔG_{II} a logarithmic linear relationship between the delamination (crack front) propagation rate da/dN and the ratio ΔG_{II} in the range of stable delamination growth was observed. There exists a threshold ΔG_{IIc} below which the delamination does not develop and a critical value of ΔG_{IIc} above which the growth is unstable.

Introduction

Laminates, in general, are assemblies of unidirectional plies oriented under 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° with respect to the main load path. Figure 1 shows a typical laminate configuration utilized in test programs. Under static tension load or cyclic loading in the tension regime, minute microcracks at the fiber/matrix interfaces are followed by more massive lateral cracks which occur first in the matrix material of the 90° -plies. In the literature such cracks are referred to as *first ply failure*. Further load increases cause additional cracks until gradually a more or less uniform pattern results. The then approximately constant spacing of the cracks is referred to as *characteristic damage state* [1]. With increasing numbers of load cycles incipient delaminations can be observed on the free edges at the interfaces of the 0° and 90° -plies which eventually merge and also progress toward the center of the specimen. Figure 1 shows radiographic evidence of the extent of edge delaminations due to cycling loading.

The nature of final failure of the specimen depends on the kind of loading. At $R = \sigma_l/\sigma_u = 0.1$ the fatigue failure is usually due to an increasing number of fiber bundle breaks in different locations, following massive degradation of the specimen by matrix cracks due to shear loading in the 0° -plies in longitudinal direction. In contrast to that the fatigue tests with different stress ratios $R = \sigma_l/\sigma_u$ indicate that in graphite-fiber-reinforced resins fatigue damage manifests itself most severely at $R = -1$. [2], [3], [4]. As depicted in Figure 2 the $\sigma - N$ -curve for multidirectional laminates tested at $R = 0.1$ is much flatter than those tested at $R = -1$ and support the supposition that the fatigue strength issue is covered by a static safety factor of $j = 1.5$ even at high cycle numbers. The fatigue strength losses at $R = -1$ is due to delaminations which develop during the compression as well as the tension load phase. At comparatively small stress ampli-

tudes corresponding to strain levels of 0.3% - 0.4%, matrix cracks develop rather early which later precipitate localized delaminations. After a period of stable delamination growth the delaminated plies tend to buckle and the subsequent instable progression of the delaminations will eventually lead to failure, the residual life depending on the strength of the remaining intact cross-sections. Based on these recognitions an analysis of delamination growth was developed with the aim of predicting the number of cycles at which buckling of delaminated plies is imminent. [2], [3], [4], [5].

The analysis method has been applied in a number of cases; however, since the delamination growth and the critical damage state in notched or unnotched multidirectional laminates are very complex issues, certain approximations had to be made. Nevertheless, the applied methodology is sound and is considered a valuable improvement of the qualitative and quantitative comprehension of the damage mechanisms in fiber-reinforced resins.

In the study of delamination development, initially in unimpaired multidirectional laminates, it became evident that the search for the locating and the tracking of the circumferential changes by nondestructive inspection is inordinately cumbersome. Therefore, test specimens with unidirectional layers were used whose central plies were separated prior to curing. See Figure 3. Such laminates are referred to as $[0_m, \theta_n]_s$, the slash indicating the cut.

Strain Energy Release Rates

The formation and propagation of cracks in laminates is accompanied by energy releases which also cause a reduction of the laminate stiffness. By establishing a relationship between the extent of damage and the change of stiffness, the energy release rate G and the stress intensity factors K can be determined. For the experimental determination of strain energy release rates and stress intensity factors different methods have been employed. In Table I standard test methods for mode I and mode II and for mode I/II are summarized. It is apparent that the majority of the methods utilize very simple test configurations which do not accurately reflect the damage mechanisms occurring in realistic environments.

Especially the cyclically changing conditions at the crack front of delaminations subjected to tension-compression loading and the unstable growth of delaminations due to buckling of delaminated plies are rarely taken into account. For that reason, new test configurations were developed which are identified by asterisks in Table I.

From the experimental evaluation of the stiffness $C \sim E$ and the delaminated area A and on the assumption that the delaminations grow at constant force F , the energy release rate G can be formulated as [6], [7]

$$G = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d(1/C)}{dA} \cdot F^2 \quad (1)$$

The total energy release rate G , in general, is composed of three contributions,

- G_I release rate due to tension
- G_{II} release rate due to shear in the delamination plane
- G_{III} release rate due to shear transverse the delamination plane.

For the problems at hand, the latter is of no consequence so that

$$G = G_I + G_{II} \quad (2)$$

The individual contributions of G_I and G_{II} are not readily separable. A numerical approximation is possible by a finite element approach which allows, by appropriate coupling of elements, the introduction of either a mode I or a mode II displacement and the simultaneous suppression of the other. [8]. Figure 4 is an example for the results of such calculations performed, in this particular case, for a propagating crack in a specimen with a transverse crack (see Figure 3 and Table I, TCTC-Test). Because of the finite dimensions of the elements, the calculations are not stable for very short cracks. Compared to the the energy release rate G_{II} the rate of G_I is very

small (about 1%) and therefore neglectable. The corresponding stress intensity factors can be obtained from the well-known relationships [9]

$$K_I = \sqrt{\frac{G_I}{R^{11}}}, \quad K_{II} = \sqrt{\frac{G_{II}}{R^{22}}}, \quad (3)$$

with
$$R^{11} = \frac{\kappa_\alpha}{\sqrt{\alpha_{11}}}, \quad R^{22} = \frac{\kappa_\alpha}{\sqrt{\alpha_{22}}}, \quad \kappa_\alpha = \sqrt{[\sqrt{\alpha_{11} \cdot \alpha_{22}} + \alpha_{12} + \frac{\alpha_{66}}{2}] \cdot \alpha_{11} \cdot \frac{\alpha_{22}}{2}},$$

and
$$\alpha_{11} = \frac{1}{E_x}, \quad \alpha_{22} = \frac{1}{E_y}, \quad \alpha_{12} = -\frac{\nu_{yx}}{E_x}, \quad \alpha_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{xy}},$$

where E_x , E_y , G_{xy} and ν_{yx} denote the inplane elastic moduli.

Strain Energy Release Rates for Unidirectional Test Specimens

In an initial study of delamination development unidirectional test specimens were used whose central plies, in accordance with Figure 3, were separated prior to curing. Such laminates are referred to $[0_n, \emptyset_m]_s$, the slash indicating the cut. In the course of cycling loading a lateral crack developed in the area of the separations from which two partial delaminations initiated at each of the interfaces of the separated and the continuous plies. The two delamination grew at uniform growth rate, but the positions of the four delamination fronts are shifted by 10 mm. After pre-determined cycle numbers the extent of the delaminations was recorded by C-scans, examples of which are given in Figure 5. Moreover X-ray examinations or a grid reflection method were used for the measurement of the delamination length. [5].

During the cycling the stiffness E of the test specimens were continually registered, so that a clear connection between the size of the delamination, a and the corresponding stiffnesses E could be established in the form of

$$\frac{E_o}{E} = 1 + \frac{t_c}{t_l} \cdot \frac{E_o}{E_l} \cdot \frac{a}{2L} \quad (4)$$

where E_o denotes the initial stiffness of the test specimen with separated plies, $E_l = E_x$ the stiffness of the fault-free laminate, L the specimen reference length, t_c the thickness of separated plies, $t_l = t - t_c$ the thickness of continuous plies and t the total thickness of the laminate. Figure 6 is a plot of the specimen stiffness rate E_o/E as a function of the delamination length a . The initial stiffness E_o has to be measured during the first loading prior to the formation of delaminations. Introducing equation (4) into equation (1) under consideration of the stiffness $C = E \cdot w \cdot t/L$, the volume $V = w \cdot t \cdot L$ and $dA = w \cdot da$, the strain energy release rate assumes the simple form

$$G_{II} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot V \cdot \sigma^2 \cdot \frac{d(1/E)}{dA} = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{\sigma^2}{E_l} \cdot \frac{t_c}{t_l} \cdot t. \quad (5)$$

The results obtained from this approach compare very favorably with the finite element calculations so that the stress intensity factor G_{II} needed for this type of delamination can be calculated rather accurately from equation (5).

In order to determine the delamination growth rate da/dN , constant amplitude tests and cyclic shedding load tests with increasing and decreasing amplitudes were conducted. This tests run with a load amplitude frequency of 5 Hz and a stress ratio of $R = 0.1$ or $R = -1$. The test specimens were preconditioned at the environmental conditions of the laboratory with a temperature of 20°C and 40% relative humidity. The results of the tests with a stress ratio of $R = 0.1$ are depicted in Figure 7. For the cyclic energy release rate ΔG_{II} , a logarithmic linear relationship between the delamination (crack front) propagation rate da/dN and the ratio ΔG_{II} in the range of stable delamination grow was observed. There exists a threshold ΔG_{IIh} below which the delamination does not develop and a critical value of ΔG_{IIc} above which the growth rate is unstable. The comparison of the results from the constant load amplitude tests with $[0_2, \emptyset_2]_s$ -specimens and

from the load shedding fatigue tests with $[0_4, \emptyset_4]_2$ -specimens indicates that the delamination growth rate da/dN is not influenced by the specimen thickness and by increasing or decreasing load amplitudes.

In corresponding experiments with a stress ratio of $R = -1$ ultimate failure of the test specimens was caused by buckling of the delaminated sections during the ultimate compression load cycle. In a number of tests the load cycling was terminated at various cycle numbers before failure and the residual static compression strength was recorded. According to Figures 8 and 9 a linear relationship was found between the length of the delamination a and the compressive strength (static or cyclic loading) of the test specimens. The solid line in the figure represents the theoretically computed buckling strength of knife-edge supported delaminated orthotropic plates [10]. The test results fit the experimental data quite well. Investigations of this kind are relatively simple and should be considered for the characterization of the notch and buckling sensitivity of fiber-reinforced resin systems in general.

Bibliography

- [1] R.D.Jamison, K.Schulte, K.L.Reifsnider and W.W.Stinchcomb: *Characterization and Analysis of Damage Mechanisms in Tension-Tension Fatigue of Graphite/Epoxy Laminates*. Published in Wilkins, D.J.: *Effects of Defects in Composite Materials*. ASTM STP 836 (1982) pp. 21 - 55.
- [2] Prinz, R.: *CRP Damage Mechanics under Fatigue Loading*. European Space Agency ESA-TT-1093 (March 1987) 287 p., Translation of: *Schadensmechanik kohlenstofffaserverstärkter Kunststoffe bei Schwingbelastung*. DFVLR-Mitteilung 87-08, 1987, 246 p.
- [3] Prinz, R.: *The Effect of Damage Development on the Compression Failure of Fatigued Multidirectional Graphite/Epoxy Laminates*. Proceedings of the International Symposium on Composite Materials and Structures. (1986) Beijing. pp. 537 - 542.
- [4] Zhao, S., R.Prinz and H.C.Goetting : *Experimental Investigations on the Damage Growth of Graphite/Epoxy Laminates with a Hole under Tension-Compression Fatigue*. ACTA AERONAUTICA ET ASTRONAUTICA SINICA 9(1988)1, pp. A75 - A83 (in chinese, ISSN 1000 6893).
- [5] Prinz, R.: *Analytical Considerations of Damage Mechanics*. In: Bergmann, H., W. et al.: *Mechanical Properties and Damage Mechanisms of Carbonfiber-Reinforced Composites - Compression Loading*. DFVLR-Mitteilung 88-41, 1988, 416 p., esp. pp. 294 - 318.
- [6] Irwin, G., R.: *Fracture*. In S.Flügge : *Handbuch der Physik, Band VI, Elastizität und Plastizität*. Springer Verlag, Berlin - Göttingen - Heidelberg, 1958, pp. 551 - 590, esp. p. 563.
- [7] O'Brien, T.K.: *Characterization of Delamination Onset and Growth in a Composite Laminate*. In K.L.Reifsnider: *Damage in Composite Materials*. ASTM STP 775 (1982) pp. 140 - 167.
- [8] Bergmann, H.W.; H.Eggers and J.Awerbuch: *Fracture Mechanics Aspects of Composite Materials*. Acta Astronautica 15(1987)3, pp. 149 - 155.
- [9] Sih, G.C.; P.C.Paris and G.R.Irwin: *On Cracks in Rectilinearly Anisotropic Bodies*. International Journal of Fracture 1(1965) pp. 189 - 203.
- [10] Shivakumar, K. and J.D.Withcomb: *Buckling of Sublaminate in a Quasi-Isotropic Composite Laminate*. Journal of Composite Materials 19(1985) pp. 2 - 18.
- [11] J.M.Whitney and C.E.Browning: *On Short-Beam Shear Tests for Composite Materials*. Experimental Mechanics, 25(1985)3 p. 294.
- [12] A.J.Smiley and R.B.Pipes: *Rate Effects on Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness in Composite Materials*. J. of Composite Materials 21 (1987) pp. 670 - 687.

- [13] W.S.Johnson and P.D.Mangalgi: *Influence of the Resin on the Interlaminar Mixed-Mode Fracture*. NASA TM 87571, 1985, 35 p.
- [14] Eggers,H., Kirschke,R. und Zick,R.: *Initiation and Propagation of Cracks in Notched Unidirectional Laminates of Carbonfiber-Reinforced Epoxy under Static Tensile Load*. DFVLR-FB 86-30 1986, 214 Seiten.

Mode	sign	designation	refer.	test configuration
I	DCB	double cantilever beam	[12] [13]	
II	TCT TCTC	transverse crack tension transverse crack tens.-comp.*	[2] [5]	
II	SBS	short beam shear	[11] [13]	
II	ENF	end-notched flexure	[13]	
I/II	CLS	crack lap shear	[13]	
I/II	EDT EDTC	edge delamination tension edge delamination tens.-comp.*	[7] [5]	
I/II	HDT HDTC	hole delamination tension hole delamination tens.-comp.*	[3] [5]	
I/II	ENT ENTC	edge notch tension edge notch tens.-comp.*	[14]	

Table 1. Tests for experimental determination of strain energy release rates for mode I and mode II and for mode I/II. New test configurations are identified by asterisks.

Figure 1. Damage states in a Laminate due to cyclic loading. Stacking order $[0_2, +45, 0_2, -45, 0, 90]_s$.

Figure 2. S - N - curves of graphite/epoxy laminates for tension-tension and tension-compression loading. Stress rates $R = \sigma_t/\sigma_u = 0,1$ and $R = -1$. $[0_2, +45, 0_2, -45, 0, 90]_s$ Stacking order. Factor of safety $j = 1.5$.

Figure 3. Test specimen with central separated plies and delaminations, emanating from the transverse crack tips. Stacking order $[0_m, \theta_n]_s$.

Figure 4. Results of numerical energy release rate calculations for G_I and G_{II} , where $a = a_1 + a_2$ is the length of the delaminations. $G_I \ll G_{II}$.

Figure 5. Ultrasonic-C-Scans of a $[0_2, \phi_2]_s$ -laminate after different numbers of load cycles.

Figure 6. Comparison of the observed delaminations length with the measured and calculated stiffness ratio E_0/E (equation 4). Initial stiffness E_0 .

Figure 7. Delamination growth rate da/dN versus cyclic energy release rate ΔG_{II} .

Figure 8. Residual compressive strength versus delamination length. Stacking order $[0_2, \phi_2]_s$. The line shows the theoretical buckling strength of the simply supported plate.

Figure 9. Residual compressive strength versus delamination length. Stacking order $[0_4, \phi_4]_s$. The line shows the theoretical buckling strength of the simply supported plate.